

Core design activities in support of the Moon Energy System with Nuclear Power (SELENE) Project: design requirements and supporting analyses

F. Lodi^{1,*}, R. Pergreff¹, M. Lach Hab¹, K. Mastrovito¹, S. Mannucci¹, C. Carrelli¹, R. Da Vià¹

¹ENEA (Nuclear Energy Systems Division), Bologna, Italy

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ABSTRACT

In the last decade, the strategic importance of the Moon has been rediscovered internationally as an environment that offers unique opportunities to increase knowledge of space and human exploration capabilities. In this context, there is a growing interest worldwide in energy solutions based on surface nuclear reactors (SNR), being a technology that allows high power densities. The SELENE project, co-funded by the Italian Space Agency (ASI), was born in this scenario as an Italian contribution to a lunar base through the conceptualization of a surface infrastructure, the Moon Energy Hub, specifically dedicated to storage and transmission of electrical and/or thermal energy produced in-situ by SNRs. In this work, preliminary activities for defining a core design of the SNR which meets the criteria of operability, reliability and compactness suitable for applications in the lunar environment are presented. Supporting neutronic and thermal-hydraulics analyses have also been performed to establish a performance envelope of the fuel assembly concept to inform subsequent design stages and arriving at a first core configuration.

Keywords: Heat Pipe Reactor, High Temperature Reactor, Neutronics, Thermal analysis, TRISO

1. INTRODUCTION

In the last decade, the strategic importance of the Moon has been rediscovered internationally as highlighted by NASA's Artemis program that targets a surface landing at the South Pole by 2027 and the China–Russia International Lunar Research Station envisioning a permanent infrastructure by 2035.

In this renewed space race, the Italian Space Agency (ASI) has decided to develop its own contribution to a lunar base. To this end, since 2024 ASI is co-financing the SELENE (Sistema Energetico Lunare con L'Energia NuclearE) project led by ENEA with partners Politecnico di Milano and Thales Alenia Space Italia. SELENE is focused on the concept of Moon Energy Hub (MEnH), responsible for the production, storage and transmission of electrical/thermal energy with one, or more, surface nuclear reactors (SNRs) at its center. The main objective of SELENE is to advance the design status and technology readiness of all the systems of the MEnH, such as the reactor, the energy conversion, the energy storage and transmission, so to pave the way for the subsequent industrialization.

The project (see Figure 1) is structured in three main phases: i) the "Scenario phase" aimed at defining the MEnH boundary conditions and requirements; ii) the "Design phase" dedicated to the conceptual design of the Hub components and their integration; iii) the "Industrialization phase" focused on consolidating the project results and preparing the subsequent stages of the strategic and industrial roadmap. Focusing on the "Design phase", after the definition of the high-level requirements for the SNR consistent with the reference mission, ENEA is leading the design of the reference SNR both in terms of the power production island and the thermal-electric conversion system.

While in [1] the focus is on the energy storage system, in this paper the preliminary work on core design which has led to a first concept definition for the fuel assembly will be laid out in terms of main requirements and design choices as well as the first supporting neutronics and thermal analyses.

*francesco.lodi@enea.it

Figure 1. High-level structure of the SELENE project.

2. THE FUEL ASSEMBLY: REQUIREMENTS AND DESIGN CHOICES

The SNR is subject to many requirements encompassing transportability, performance, safety, environment etc. which must be translated into proper design choices able to satisfy the envisaged specifications. The most relevant high-level requirements impacting the preliminary core design are:

- rating of 100 kW_e for 10 years (based on identified opportunity window);
- simplified fuel procurement and transport;
- compactness and weight limits;
- maximize reliance on passive systems for core functions;
- maximize conversion and heat dissipation efficiencies.

Based on the above and further more detailed requirements, along with the experience accumulated in the framework of a feasibility study performed by ENEA and co-financed by ASI [2], it was decided to employ:

- HALEU TRISO-type fuel for manufacturing flexibility and high temperature operations;
- sodium Heat Pipes (HP) for efficient heat removal at high temperatures with no moving parts;
- a solid hydride moderator and inverted-fuel concept (i.e., where the classical positions of fuel and moderator/coolant are swapped) to limit the weight and size of the core as much as possible. The inverted concept, indeed, allows to avoid the use of additional structural materials while allowing the moderator to be housed in pins, to the benefit of hydrogen retention.

Manufacturing and dimensions constraints analysis for an inverted-fuel concept, as well as preliminary thermal-hydraulics and neutronic analyses lead to the selection of a Fuel Assembly-based (FA) approach instead of a monolithic core. As visible in Figure 2 the first FA concept is an hexagonal fuel compact comprising TRISO particles with 40% packing fraction within a silicon carbide (SiC) matrix. The fuel compact has cylindrical cavities to host moderator pins and sodium HPs. As first reference choices the moderator selected has been zirconium hydride in delta-phase while HPs can employ stainless steel wick (for screen mesh) and a Ni-based superalloy for the casing. This concept of FA will be the subject of a feasibility study performed by a TRISO manufacturer within the SPACE IT UP! project [3], financed by ASI, which aims to strengthen Italian technology for use in the exploration and exploitation of space.

3. NUMERICAL ANALYSES SUPPORTING THE DESIGN

As usual, design choices must be supported by numerical analyses. At this stage, these analyses are limited to the FA level; nevertheless, they provide important insights into the modeling approaches adopted and key physical aspects of this configuration to inform subsequent design stages. The main results obtained so far are discussed in the following, adopting the traditional distinction between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics.

3.1. Neutronics

The main neutronic results in terms of criticality, spectrum, spectral index, moderation ratio, reactivity swing and mass balance are presented below. Due to the specific modeling issues of a fuel (TRISO) characterized by particles randomly dispersed in a matrix, two different approaches were simultaneously used to be aware of their effects on the neutronic parameters above. These are:

- a heterogeneous modeling of the fuel region (reference modeling);
- a homogeneous modeling of the fuel region.

It should be emphasized that the two approaches differ only in modeling the fuel region, every other FA region being the same. For the heterogeneous modeling (hereinafter heterogeneous case), the Monte Carlo code MCNP6.3 [4] was used because, thanks to the URAN card which randomly translates the TRISO kernel inside the lattice elements, it allows a close approximation of the real case [5]. For the homogeneous modeling (hereinafter homogeneous case), in addition to MCNP, the Monte Carlo code OpenMC [6] was used (thanks to its modular and open-source architecture, enabling an easier coupling with the CFD code OpenFOAM used for thermal-hydraulic analyses). In this case, the homogenization was done according to the volume-weighted homogenization (VWH) method, a technique that requires the definition of an *ad hoc* mixture that preserves the volumes of the materials. From a neutronic point of view, one of the main effects of this modeling is that, by moving from a heterogeneous to a homogeneous description, the resonance escape probability (p) i.e., the probability that neutrons escape capture during slowing down, is reduced with a consequent underestimation of the criticality. The cross-sectional views of the two FAs thus obtained are shown in Figure 2. Specifically, regarding the heterogeneous case view in Figure 2, it should be noted that it does not exactly represent the geometry obtained with the URAN card, since the kernel positions are fixed and centered in the lattice cells and not, as it should be, randomly arranged in them. Moreover, it is also worth noting that, in the hexagonal cells intersected by the cylinders (whether heat pipes or moderators), the packing fraction (i.e., the ratio in the fuel region of particles volume and fuel compact volume) is not preserved. Although this causes a change in the physics of these cells that partially affects the criticality of the system, this effect has been neglected at this stage.

Figure 2. Cross-sectional views of the FA with a heterogeneous (left) and homogeneous (right) modeling. Fuel compact (fuchsia), moderator (yellow) and HP (orange/azure/green) are visible.

All neutronic calculations were performed with radial and axial reflective boundary conditions. At this stage, no thermal expansion was considered and all densities are at room temperature (293 K) except those of the vapor and liquid sodium inside the heat pipes which are set to operating temperatures. Moreover, since we do not yet have thermal feedback, all material temperatures for Doppler broadening of the cross-sections are set to 1200 K. The ENDF/B-VIII.0 distribution [7] in ACE format was used as the evaluated nuclear data library. The depletion calculation strategy is performed to attain a total average burnup of 18267 MWd/MTU with a FA power of 9.09 kW (1/55 of the total thermal power assuming 55 FA are assumed needed for a core) and an availability factor of 100 %. To account for the physical phenomena typical of thermal spectrum reactors, 26 depletion steps are defined, with a finer discretization in the early steps. In OpenMC the depletion calculations were performed using the CE/CM type numerical integration algorithm as in MCNP. Moreover, the normalization method of the

reaction rates during burnup evolution was based on the fission energy values of the involved isotopes as found in the literature.

The infinite multiplication factors at beginning of life (BOL) of the two FAs are shown in Table I. As can be seen, the agreement between the two codes in the homogeneous case is very good. In fact, their difference, that is approximately 50 pcm, is not significant because the statistical uncertainties (3σ) of the calculations partially overlap. Much more relevant is, instead, the difference in criticality between the heterogeneous and homogeneous cases. In fact, the homogeneous case results in an underestimation of the criticality of approximately 700 pcm due to the reduction of the resonance self-shielding of the fuel. A further criticality calculation (Table I) was performed using a homogenization method – the reactivity-equivalent physical transformation (RPT) method [8] – specifically designed for this type of calculations. This method appropriately modifies materials and geometries to preserve the reactivity of the heterogeneous case. The RPT method should be understood as a computationally efficient, core-level solution, able to still capture the underlying physics leading to criticality.

Table I. k_{inf} [-] at BOL.

Case \ Code	MCNP6.3	1σ	OpenMC	1σ
FA with heterogeneous fuel region (URAN card)	1.41373	17	–	–
FA with fuel region homogenized by VWH method	1.40686	17	1.40741	14
FA with fuel region homogenized by RPT method	–	–	1.41459	11

Figure 3. Spectrum for the homogeneous and heterogeneous cases (left) and their spectral difference (right).

The normalized fluxes per unit lethargy in the FA calculated with MCNP at BOL for the heterogeneous and homogeneous cases are plotted in the left panel of Figure 3. The relative percentage error to one standard deviation of the spectrum values is always less than 0.3 % except for the five fast groups with maximum energy for which it increases up to 2.3 %. Although the two spectra nearly coincide visually, the main spectral differences between the two cases occur at thermal energies, as shown in the right panel of Figure 3. In percentage terms, this means an error on the thermal spectrum in the homogeneous case of about -2.3 %. This difference is reflected in an increase in the spectral index (here defined as the ratio between fast and thermal flux), that goes from 3.25 (heterogeneous case) to 3.32 (homogeneous case). Regarding the spectral index, it is worth noting that even in the heterogeneous case its value could be further reduced increasing moderation. At the same time, it must be taken into account that the margins for increasing moderation (and therefore the thermal part of the spectrum and, consequently, the criticality) are limited. In fact, for safety-related reasons, the ratio between kernel (UO_2) and moderator volumes (which is 16.8 %) cannot fall below 13 %. Otherwise, a condition of overmoderation would be reached, as can be seen in Figure 4 in the moderation ratio curve obtained with OpenMC for the homogeneous case. The curve was calculated assuming that the density of zirconium hydride is constant at room temperature (i.e., neglecting variations in hydrogen concentration that, at operating temperature and in the absence of a suitable barrier, would occur due

to gradients in concentration and temperature). The one-standard-deviation statistical uncertainty associated with the k_{inf} values in Figure 4 is at most 30 pcm.

Figure 4. Moderation ratio of the FA with the homogeneous fuel region.

To obtain a general indication of the FA performance over its operational lifetime, a depletion calculation was performed. For both cases (Figure 4 left), a reactivity swing (i.e., the difference in criticality between the beginning and the end of life - EOL) of approximately 6800 pcm was obtained with MCNP. In Figure 5 (right), for the homogeneous case, the algebraic difference between the multiplication factors calculated with MCNP and OpenMC at each burnup step is shown. The random scatter of the data points indicates the absence of any systematic simulation bias. Moreover, all points (except one) fall within two standard deviations, demonstrating very good agreement between the two sets of results. As a result of the depletion calculation, the mass balance for some fuel isotopes was evaluated as the difference between their values at EOL and BOL. As shown in Table II, the agreement between the two cases and, in the homogeneous case, between the two codes is good overall.

Figure 5. $k_{inf} [-]$ as a function of burnup (left) and Δk [pcm] between the two codes at each burnup step (right).

Table II. Mass balance (mass at EOL – mass at BOL).

Case \ Isotope	²³⁵ U		²³⁸ U		²³⁹ Pu	
	MCNP	OpenMC	MCNP	OpenMC	MCNP	OpenMC
FA (heterogeneous fuel region)	-41.40 g	-	-8.00 g	-	+5.67 g	-
FA (homogeneous fuel region)	-41.40 g	-41.22 g	-8.00 g	-8.44 g	+6.04 g	+6.10 g

3.2. Thermal-hydraulics

3.2.1. Heat Pipe Technology

As explained in Section 2, the reference technology for heat removal is HP, a passive device that exploits evaporation and condensation of a working fluid to transfer heat. An HP is structurally composed of three parts – the vapor chamber that hosts the vapor phase emerging from the evaporator, the wick, a porous or grooved medium through which the condensed working fluid returns to the evaporator, and the casing as an outer enclosure. Moreover, an HP is characterized by theoretical limits, based on hydrodynamic conditions of/and between phases, their interactions, and incipient boiling conditions that can be reached under certain thermal conditions. For this reason, understanding and evaluating these limits was the first step in characterizing the heat pipe design.

Figure 6. Performance Limit Curves for Screen Mesh and Grooved Heat Pipe.

Based on a rating power of 100 kW_e, an energy conversion efficiency of 20%, two HPs per assembly and 55 FA, a preliminary design was developed in which each HP handles around 5 kW of thermal power, with a nominal optimal working condition for the conversion system of 1100 K (hot sink). Furthermore, if a typical heat power distribution within the core is assumed, the target heat-removal capacity must be designed to accommodate a peak power 25 % above the average value. In addition, a preliminary overpower safety margin of 15 % is applied. Therefore, each heat pipe was sized to handle at least 7.2 kW of thermal power.

Limits evaluation – namely the sonic, viscous, entrainment, capillary, and boiling limits [9] - for different geometrical configurations for both screen mesh and grooved wick heat pipes were investigated to select the most suitable one, based on vapor chamber radius, wick thickness, permeability and effective pore radius, groove channels geometry and HP length. Screen mesh HP is characterized by higher capillarity and lower between-phases friction, while the grooved one has higher phases friction, good capillarity, and lower liquid phase resistance within the wick that helps for long HPs. Moreover, grooved heat pipe allows a smaller wick thickness. The upper limits of the dimensions were set via a trade-off between the expected performance to be achieved, the target number of HPs and the size of the other elements present in the core. The corresponding limits curves for a selected HP configuration and the two wick types are shown in Figure 6. In the screen mesh HP, the entrainment at lower temperature and the boiling limit at higher temperature approach the operating point, consequently, rapid temperature transients should be carefully monitored in both cases. The grooved HP has a larger boiling limit margin, but startup or lower temperature operations must be carefully controlled to reach the operating point without exceeding the power-handling capability defined by the entrainment limit.

3.2.2. Thermal Modeling with CFD code

More detailed thermal analyses are required to evaluate the HPs thermal capabilities. For this reason, thermal models of a stand-alone HP and of a first FA concept were developed in OpenFOAM [10]. The stand-alone HP model consists of three regions – the casing, wick, and vapor channel – each modeled as a solid. The choice of modeling all domains as pure solids is a common practice in the HPs analysis, providing a simplified approach that requires low computational effort while still offering a good representation of the physics. The wick is characterized by equivalent transport and thermal properties, evaluated by approximately averaging the properties of the solid structure and liquid sodium, assuming negligible advective heat transport. The vapor chamber is modeled as an equivalent solid thermal model, where an equivalent thermal conductivity was used to represent the latent heat of vaporization carried by the vapor mass flow rate from the evaporator to the condenser. Thermophysical properties of the vapor channel correspond to those of vapor in saturated conditions and the equivalent thermal conductivity can be expressed starting either by the Darcy's law [9] or the Fick's law [11]. The HP model was subjected to, and it is currently undergoing, a validation process to assess its predictive capability. The approach involves the comparison of simulations outcomes with experimental data available in literature. Table III shows an example of the comparison of tabulated experimental results for a sodium HP, with an imposed heat power flux at the evaporator, cooled down by an air jacket at the condenser [12]. Errors are coherent with the current accuracy needs but improvement strategies with tuning parameters to improve model predictability are under analysis.

Table III. Experimental vs OpenFOAM casing temperature comparison with data in [12].

Axial Position [m]		0.10	0.20	0.30	0.10	0.50	0.60	0.70	0.80
Casing T [K]	Experimental	1176.3	1186.6	1167.4	1171.9	1113.0	1113.7	1116.8	1111.1
	OpenFOAM	1165.6	1165.6	1165.6	1165.6	1133.4	1133.4	1133.4	1133.4
Error [K] (abs)		10.7	21	1.8	6.3	20.4	19.7	16.6	22.3

Figure 7. Central Assembly Cross Section (left) and Vertical Assembly Cross Section (right).

A first thermal analysis was thus possible, where adiabatic boundary conditions were set for all the surfaces except the condenser wall of the HPs, to which a fixed temperature was imposed considering the optimal nominal temperature for the conversion system. An internal power within the fuel of 9.09 kW, corresponding to the average thermal power produced by the single assembly, was used. In Figure 7 the radial and azimuthal temperature distributions for two selected cross sections of the assembly are shown. These results provide an initial estimation of the temperature gradients across the assembly and the peak temperature within each domain, allowing an assessment of whether the selected materials can safely operate under the expected thermal conditions. For the moderator region, it also serves as input for future hydrogen-diffusion modeling, which will be relevant for subsequent neutronic evaluations. Moreover, it provides insight into how HP arrangement can affect temperature distribution, thus leading to an improved overall configuration for the full core.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The first concept of FA was developed and analyzed from the neutronics and thermal-hydraulics point of view making it possible to establish first calculational models and as well as understanding its basic performance. The gained insights will be exploited in defining a viable core configuration that, together with control, safety and shielding elements, can fully satisfy the established high-level requirements. In parallel, from the computational side, models will be further refined so to cope with the increased complexity of the system to be studied as well as the higher accuracy and range of analyses required. Time-dependent HP performance models will be further developed to enable pre- and post-test analyses of the experimental test section to be deployed in the project to characterize the reference design.

More generally, the SELENE project, which is currently focused on the design of the main components of the Hub, and the SIU! project were introduced. The ambitions of the SELENE project go beyond the design phase encompassing the establishment of a programmatic roadmap, including research and development activities still needed, regulatory gaps and supply chains considerations, to further propel the Italian industrial landscape in the race for the Moon. SIU! Will instead be a stepping stone to further increase confidence on the design maturity of the proposed FA concept.

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